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In the development of a Knowledge Graph for Electoral Studies

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Abstract: This report details how involvement of the user community will be organised in the development of a Knowledge Graph in electoral studies in the SSHOC project. It presents how the user community can be identified, discusses forms of involvement, and ways in which members of the user community can be reached and recruited in the development of the Knowledge Graph.

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes SSHOC Deliverable 9.8, which describes the planned *User Community Involvement in the Development of a Knowledge Graph for Electoral Studies*. The report links up closely with the reports of Deliverable D9.6 (*Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community*) and Deliverable 9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*). These two earlier reports and the current one prepare the specification and planning of Deliverable 9.9, which is the production and delivery of a Knowledge Graph in electoral studies. The report of D9.6 defined the substantive research field and the scholarly community for which the Knowledge Graph is intended. D9.7 provided specification and planning of the development of the Knowledge Graph and emphasised the need for end-user involvement in its development. The current report (D9.8) details the various forms that user involvement can take, and how members of the user community are to be reached and recruited.

The rationale underlying the need for user involvement is to avoid that the functionality of the Knowledge Graph to be produced does not match needs and expectations of end-users, which would result in suboptimal usage in and by the user community and obstruct further development of the Knowledge Graph after its initial delivery. The main elements for which user community involvement will be planned are:

- Providing feedback on functionality at various stages of development
- Contributing to ontology development
- Crowd-contributing to classification of materials as a basis for training of algorithms
- Beta testing

Additionally, all forms of involvement of the user communities will help promote awareness of and familiarity with EOSC/SSHOC and its products, tools and services.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CSES	Comparative Study of Electoral Studies
DVPW	Deutsche Vereinigung für Politikwissenschaft (German Political Science Association)
EES	European Election Study
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOP	Elections, Public Opinion and Parties
ISSP	International Social Survey Program
JEPOP	Journal of Election, Public Opinion and Parties
KG	Knowledge Graph
MEDem	Monitoring Electoral Democracy Consortium
MEDW	Making Electoral Democracy Work
NES	National Election Study
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
TEV	True European Voter Consortium

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1. Introduction and purpose of this deliverable

Work package 9 (WP9 –*Data Communities*) of the SSHOC project focuses on various user communities, including some that are not represented by any of the partners of the Consortium. One of these is the user community working in the field of Electoral Studies, which is an important and highly developed field in Political Science and cognate disciplines. This user community has been defined and demarcated in the report of Deliverable D9.6 (*Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community*).

The program of activities of WP9 includes piloting the development of infrastructural tools – known as Knowledge Graphs. The design of such a pilot Knowledge Graph (KG) in Electoral Studies has been specified in the report of Deliverable 9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*). In this report of Deliverable D9.7 the need for involvement of the relevant user community is strongly emphasised (see its Sections 4 and 7) for reasons that are summarised as follows:

- *Avoiding the development of a KG of which the functionality does not match needs and expectations of end-users, which would then lead to suboptimal usage in and by the user community and to obstruct further development of the KG beyond the timeline of the deliverables involved;*
- *Providing feedback at various stages of development*
- *Contributing to ontology development*
- *Crowd-contributing to classification of materials as a basis for training of algorithms*
- *Beta testing*

Additionally, all forms of involvement of relevant user communities will help promote awareness of and familiarity with EOSC/SSHOC and its products, tools and services.

The current report, which constitutes Deliverable D9.8 (*User Community Involvement Plan*) specifies how the desired user community involvement will be organised, and how members of the user community will be approached and recruited. This report will not elaborate in great detail the various substantive tasks in which members of the user community are hoped to play a role, because those tasks have been described in detail in the report of Deliverable D9.7 (together with the relevant context in which those tasks will have to be performed, namely the development and production of the intended Knowledge Graph).

This report starts, in section 2 with brief description of the user community whose involvement is sought, in the form of a summary of the report of Deliverable D9.6 (*Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community*). This section aims to clarify the character of the user community that is the intended beneficiary of the development of the pilot Knowledge Graph, and whose feedback and contribution to that development is desired.

Section 3 distinguishes various forms in which members of the user community are intended to be involved in the development of the Knowledge Graph. This is combined with a discussion of strategies of recruitment of

members of the user community for these various forms of involvement (section 4). Section 4 contains the main conclusions.

2. The field and user community of electoral studies

2.1. Demarcation

The field of electoral studies, and thus its user community, is characterised by its focus on the study of elections. As indicated in the report of D9.6 (*'Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community'*), this domain is – in spite of this shared focus– broad and variegated. Yet, as elaborated also in the report of D9.6 a clearly recognisable dominant core of this user community exists that can be described as follows:

- An **empirical** orientation on the study of elections. Although the field, and thus also the user community that occupies this field, contains important philosophical, normative, and 'positive' (in the sense of non-empirical axiomatic-deductive) work, its larger part is oriented to the empirical study of elections.
- A focus on **free and fair elections**. Elections are not the exclusive domain of democratic societies or organisations and are also conducted in non-democratic contexts. All of these are potential, and occasionally actual object of scholarly research, but studies of elections that are not free and fair are relatively rare, while the great bulk of research is devoted to elections that are (relatively) free and fair.
- An orientation on **elections for state offices**. Elections are conducted for positions in all kinds of contexts, including churches, labour unions, civic organisations, sports clubs, pressure groups, political parties, and so forth. Yet, although all such elections are potential objects for empirical study, actual research is focussed most frequently by far on elections for state offices.
- An orientation at the **national level**. In states, elections are generally conducted for offices at different levels of organisation, from local, to regional and subsequently to national offices. Of all of these, those at the national level attract by far the most scholarly attention. This national focus can also be observed in elections for non-state offices (e.g., elections for the national executive of labour unions are studied considerably more frequently than those for shop stewards).
- A focus on the **behaviour of voters**. Elections are complex interactions between quite different kinds of actors, including voters, candidates (and groupings of candidates most often referred to as political parties), media, sponsors and financiers, opinion leaders and social influencers, professionals for hire (pollsters, campaign consultants), regulators, and so on. Here too, the behaviour (and the consequences of that behaviour) of each of these kinds of actors is studied in the field of electoral studies, but –when looking at quantities of publication output– the behaviour of voters is by far the most popular topic for research, followed (at some distance) by studies about the behaviour of candidates and parties, with studies of all other kinds of actors being quite sporadic.

- A dominant disciplinary orientation in **political science**. Smaller segments of the electoral studies domain are located in other disciplines such as sociology, psychology, law, economics, geography, communication, and so forth.
- A dominant focus on **'who wins?' as key outcome**. Elections fulfil multiple functions, and their outcomes are therefore varied. Such outcomes may include phenomena such as legitimacy, accountability, representation, agenda-setting, policy-direction, democratic development (or, conversely, backsliding), etcetera. Yet, and again gauging by volumes of research output, the most frequently studied key outcome of elections can be defined in terms of the 'who wins?' question.

The demarcation of the core of the field of electoral studies (and its associated user community) above is not, nor is it meant to be, exhaustive. It is partly descriptive, and partly indicative. This demarcation is thus unavoidably somewhat incomplete, and it does not aim to classify researchers or research projects as unequivocally being part of the field and user community of electoral studies or as part of other fields of research. Indeed, such questions are sterile and futile in view of overlaps between different disciplines, subdisciplines and fields of study. The attempt to demarcate the core of the field is motivated by a search for user communities and scholars who can fruitfully be included in the efforts of WP9 to develop the aspired Knowledge Graph in electoral studies. It is thus intended to be more of instrumental than of intrinsic value.

The pilot-Knowledge Graph aims to be of direct interest and relevance for the largest possible proportion of the overall user community in electoral studies. It does so by focussing on the dominant core of the user community, as described above: empirical studies of citizen/voter behaviour in elections for national-level public office in democratic societies. Yet, even this restriction of the domain to be covered by the pilot-Knowledge Graph still leaves a very wide and diverse field of scholarly work. This is because citizen/voter behaviour encompasses widely diverse phenomena. These include whether or not people make use of their right to vote; their choice of candidate or party; their activities in electoral processes as influencer, canvasser, volunteer, donor; and even more. A further narrowing down of the substantive domain of the pilot-Knowledge Graph is therefore necessary. This was achieved by a focus on *electoral participation*, which involves whether or not people who have the right to vote do make use of that right in a given election by casting a vote. In spite of this narrowing down, the pilot-Knowledge Graph can be expected to be of direct interest to very large segments of the electoral studies user community. It focuses on one of the central questions in very many studies of citizen/voter behaviour; it links up directly to virtually all empirical studies of citizen/voter behaviour and understanding differences in electoral participation between elections or between countries is one of the dominating questions in much comparative electoral research.¹

¹ It must be emphasised that, although closely linked, electoral participation is to be distinguished from its aggregate manifestation, which is the *rate* of electoral participation, also known as the *turnout* of an election. Turnout is an aggregate-level phenomenon, while electoral participation is individual-level. Although the two terms are often used somewhat interchangeably, they refer to different units of observation and analysis, and therefore relate also to different research questions, explanatory approaches and empirical insights.

2.2. Identifying user communities

The notion of user communities has been discussed extensively in the report of Deliverable D9.1 (*Challenges that user communities face when attempting to contribute to SSHOC*). In that report it was emphasised that user communities can be defined in terms of their shared interest and active research involvement in a given field of study. In spite of these shared characteristics, these communities are often quite heterogeneous qua disciplinary background, ontological and epistemological assumptions, and empirical approaches. Moreover, active researchers are often part of multiple user communities. This diversity implies that identifying user communities (and reaching their members) is best achieved by organisations that represent them.² Such organisations exist in various forms, the most important of which are dedicated professional organisations, dedicated scholarly conferences, dedicated publication outlets, and domain-specific tools and resources. Each of these has been discussed in detail in the report of Deliverable D9.6 (*Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community*) and will be summarised below.³

- **Professional organisations**

The field of electoral studies is mostly located in Political Science and many scholars in electoral studies are therefore professionally organised in national political science associations. Although many of these associations contain organised sections for sub-disciplines such as for electoral studies, not all of such organised sections are equally active in organising and representing their respective user communities. Two of such organised sections that are consistently active in organising events for their respective communities are the *Arbeitskreis Wahlen und Politische Einstellungen* of the German Political Science Association (DVPW),⁴ and the Specialist Group on *Elections, Public Opinion and Parties* (EPOP) of the British Political Science Association (PSA).⁵ Each has several hundred individual members, each organizes dedicated conferences and publications for their community, and each regularly informs its membership about sundry matters deemed to be of shared interest. Each of these constitutes therefore an appropriate platform for approaching a (nationally organised) segment of the wider user community of electoral studies.

Another potentially relevant organization –still under development– is **MEDem** (Monitoring Electoral Democracy), which is an emerging European research infrastructure that connects many existing comparative and national projects in the field of electoral studies. It aims to gain a position on the ESFRI roadmap as a central and strategically important hub for electoral research. Its foundational

² These organisations are elsewhere referred to more generally as the stakeholder group of researchers (see the description of the SSHOC engagement and communication strategy at https://zenodo.org/record/3592244#Xvnck_kzapo). In the context of EOSC they are known as “Learned societies, research communities, scientific and professional associations” (see, e.g., <https://eoscpilot.eu/sites/default/files/eoscpilot-d8.5-v1.1.pdf>). For the purposes of the current report the more fine-grained distinctions used here are preferred.

³ Refer to D9.6 Section 3 for further details.

⁴ See <https://www.politik.uni-mainz.de/dvpw-wahlen/> [24.06.2020]

⁵ See Political Studies Association: <https://www.psa.ac.uk/specialist-groups/epop> [29.06.2020]

meeting is planned for the spring of 2020. Once established, MEDem could be a strategically important partner for reaching user communities in electoral studies.

- **Scholarly conferences in the field of electoral studies**

Scholarly conferences are amongst the most productive venues to contact and inform active researchers in order to obtain their potential collaboration in the development of the Knowledge Graph in electoral studies. The relevance of a specific conference depends on how closely it is tied to the field of electoral studies. Large discipline-wide conferences are thus of limited value. The most relevant conferences for the purpose of engaging the electoral studies user community are those that are entirely devoted to electoral studies. Both of the organisations mentioned in the previous bullet point do organise such conferences. The *Arbeitskreis Wahlen und Politische Einstellungen* usually has its annual conference in late Spring or early Summer (May/June), while the Specialist Group on *Elections, Public Opinion and Parties* has its annual conference in September.

In view of the Covid-19 pandemic, both conferences have been cancelled for 2020.

- **Dedicated publication outlets for the field of electoral studies**

Publication outlets that are widely regarded as emblematic for a field are excellent ways of identifying and reaching user communities. Research in electoral studies is published in a great number of journals in political science and cognate disciplines, most of which are not exclusively dedicated to this field. At the time of writing only four scholarly journals exist that focus exclusively on electoral research: *Electoral Studies* (commercially published by Elsevier), *Journal of Elections, Public Opinion and Parties* (published by Routledge under the auspices of the EPOP specialist Group), *Japanese Journal of Electoral Studies* (Published by the Japanese Association of Electoral Studies), and *Journal of Electoral Studies* (published by the Election Study Center, National Chengchi University Taipei). The overwhelming majority of articles in the last two of these journals are published in Japanese, respectively Chinese, which strongly limits their relevance for western or wider international audiences. The first two of these journals, however, are internationally very well-known and enjoy a solid scholarly reputation, as reflected in various bibliometric indices. They constitute therefore an excellent basis for identifying research-active members of the electoral studies user community.

- **Dedicated resources for the field of electoral studies**

User communities can be identified by their utilisation of crucial resources and tools that are of specific importance to them, and that are widely shared by members of the community. For the field of electoral studies such resources consist particularly of data. Historically, the development of the field is strongly connected to the emergence of 'national election studies' (NESs). These are large-scale surveys of voters, conducted in election contexts, that focus on citizens' electoral behaviour and their relevant attitudes and orientations. These studies yield data that are generally made available to the entire scientific community as soon as possible, making NESs core infrastructural projects for their respective (national) communities of electoral scholars. Data from these studies are invariably

professionally curated, usually via data archives such as DANS (in the Netherlands), GESIS (in Germany), and their counterparts in many other countries. These data are among the most widely shared resources in the social sciences in general, and in the community of electoral studies scholars in particular. Moreover, these studies have become indispensable for comparative electoral research as they are the basis for comparative projects such as the CSES⁶, the 'European Voter' (cf. Thomassen 2005), and the TEV project,⁷ all of which generated extensive comparative data resources that were made available, virtually without restrictions, for scholarly communities in electoral studies and beyond.

The discussion above evidenced that the user community of electoral studies can be effectively identified through the four routes identified: professional organisations, scholarly conferences, dedicated publication outlets, and dedicated core data resources. Section 3 discusses how these options will be leveraged in order to involve the user community in the development of the Knowledge Graph in electoral studies.

⁶ See website of the Comparative Study of Electoral systems: <https://cses.org/> [24.06.2020]

⁷ See website of MZES: <http://www.mzes.uni-mannheim.de/d7/en/projects/the-true-european-voter-a-strategy-for-analysing-the-prospects-of-european-electoral-democracy-that-includes-the-west> [27.06.2020]

3. Planning of desired user community involvement

As elaborated in detail in the report of Deliverable D9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*), the development of the Knowledge Graph in electoral studies may be enhanced by user community involvement in different forms and different stages.⁸ Those forms will be summarised here, while referring to the original report for further detail:

- **Feedback on intended functionality**

An initial online survey can be launched to measure the frequency and relevance of potential questions that the pilot- Knowledge Graph can answer. This will guarantee that the developed product will be effectively addressing researchers' genuine demands.

- **Ontology development**

Particularly in the development of ontology involvement of leading and expert members of the user community of Electoral Studies is expected to be of crucial importance. In some instances, such experts can be involved in a decentralised and on-line fashion, while in other instances face-to-face consultations with several of such experts are expected to be of particular value.

Such face-to-face encounters were originally envisaged –and already planned– to take place in the context of relevant meetings and conferences in the field of electoral studies.⁹ Unfortunately, these planned encounters had to be cancelled in view of the Covid-19 pandemic, and small-group online video conferencing equivalents of the originally planned meetings are being prepared for being conducted in the summer of 2020.

The expert members of the user community sought for this particular form of involvement will be invited to take part on a personal basis by their colleagues who are working on the development of the Knowledge Graph (particularly from the University of Nottingham and the University of Vienna).

Following the development of initial versions of the ontology, all members of the user community will be invited to assess, consolidate, and extend it.

- **Crowd-contributing to classification of materials as a basis for training of algorithms**

⁸ Any online or off-line workshops or events in this context will be organised in collaboration with work packages 2 and 6 of the SSHOC project.

⁹ Cancelled meetings included a workshop with *DACH*, the Austrian-German-Swiss-electoral workshop; the annual meeting of the *Arbeitskreis Wahlen und Politische Einstellungen* of the German Political Science Association (DVPW), and the annual meeting of the EPOP group of the British Political Studies Association.

End-users will be recruited to assist in classifying publications and datasets.¹⁰ Most notably, the content of publications will need to be coded with regard to theories, concepts, and research methods. The manually coded documents will then be used as training material for algorithms that automatically classify new publications along those dimensions. Here, the expertise of the members could, for example, be leveraged by assigning documents to be classified to those who have cited these works in their own publications. Likewise, the national teams of election studies can be asked to classify their datasets to the extent that current meta-data (e.g. keywords) does not yet provide sufficient information on the concepts measured by the surveys.

- **Testing**

As detailed in the report of Deliverable 9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*). Crowdsourcing mechanisms will be used to guarantee user community involvement in the various stages of testing.¹¹

- **Post-delivery development**

The Knowledge Graph is intended to become a part of the infrastructure of the user community in electoral studies. To fulfil that function it needs regular maintenance and updating, in addition to a gradual expansion of its currently intended domain of electoral participation, to include also other aspects of (the study) of voter behaviour, and other elements of the field of electoral studies. It is therefore necessary that some kind of organisation assumes responsibility for all these aspects of post-delivery maintenance, upgrading, refinement and expansion, including roles of data-stewardship and the organisers of user community involvement. Such an organisation would need to have a relatively stable organisational basis and would need to be a legitimate and authoritative body representing the user community of electoral studies. As discussed in section 2 of this report the user community currently lacks such organisations. However, the MEDem initiative is well placed to remedy this.¹²

¹⁰ This will be done during the summer of 2020 and continue for as long as necessary. In view of the fact that the development of a Knowledge Graph is a process of continuous and iterative development, the various user-involvement tasks are of a continuous nature and do not have a single endpoint.

¹¹ Testing will occur in various forms and at various stages, as detailed in the report of Deliverable 9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*). Earliest aspects of testing will take place in the early fall of 2020, comprehensive pre-delivery testing will be conducted early in 2021. However, in view of the iterative nature of the development of the Knowledge Graph, that will hopefully continue post-delivery, testing, and user-involvement in testing, will remain relevant throughout the entire life cycle of the Knowledge Graph.

¹² MEDem is an emerging European research infrastructure that connects many existing comparative and national projects in the field of electoral studies. It aims to gain a position on the ESFRI roadmap as a central and strategically important hub for electoral research. Its foundational meeting took place in February 2020. Once firmly established, MEDem could be an obvious body to assume responsibilities for the post-delivery aspects of maintenance and further development of the Knowledge Graph.

Discussions with MEDem are planned to establish the role it can play in post-delivery maintenance and further development.

Recruitment for crowd-sourced user community involvement

Originally a two-pronged approach was envisaged for recruiting members of the user community in the various activities referred to above. One prong was via relevant conferences and scientific meetings, the second was via online recruitment. Because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the first of these opportunities is not feasible, at least for some time, and only the second approach remains viable.

Online recruitment will be based on an indirect approach of members of the user community, using organisations and other intermediaries who are likely to maintain lists of members, of users, of interested scholars. The group working on the development of the Knowledge Graph will approach these intermediary organisations with a request to alert their members to a set of online resources in which the aim of the intended Knowledge Graph is described and explained, and where researchers in the field of electoral studies are invited to contribute in the forms described above. The same approach will be followed via the executive teams of National Election Studies (and other relevant survey programs) and the data providers of those NESs (these are listed in Table 1).

Additionally, the team will compile itself a list of relevant members of the user community consisting of authors of relevant scholarly articles, starting with the journals referred to above (see section 2), and possibly extending this to authors of papers in relevant sections of conferences, etc. The activities listed here will take place during summer and early fall of 2020 and continue for as long as necessary.

Table 1: National election study and other relevant survey programs

National election study program	Since	Data provider
Australian Election Study (AES)	1987	Australian Data Archive (ADA)
Austrian National Election Study (AUTNES)	2008	Austrian Social Science Data Archive (AUSSDA)
Belgian National Election Study (BNES)	1991	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
Canadian Election Study (CES)	1965	Canadian Opinion Research Archive (CORA)
Danish National Election Study (DNES)	1971	Centre for survey and Survey/Register data (CSSR)
Estonian National Election Study (ENES)	2003	Estonian National Election Study (ENES)
Finnish National Election Study (FNES)	2003	Finish Social Science Data Archive (FSD)
French Election Study (FES)	1958	French Data Archive For Social Sciences (CDSP)
German Longitudinal Election Study (GLES)	1949	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
British Election Study (BES)	1963	UK Data Service
Hellenic National Election Studies (ELNES)	2009	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)
Hungarian Election Study	1996	TÁRKI Social Research Institute (TARKI)
Icelandic National Election Study (ICENES)	1983	Social Science Research Institute (SSRI)
Irish National Election Study (INES)	2002	Irish Social Science Data Archive (ISSDA)
Israel National Election Studies (INES)	1969	Israel National Election Studies (INES)

Italian National Election Study (ITANES)	1968	Italian National Election Study (ITANES)
Japanese Election Study (JES)	1983	Social Science Japan Data Archive (SSJDA)
Lithuanian National Election Study (LNES)	2012	Lietuvos HSM duomenų archyvas (LiDA)
Dutch Parliamentary Election Studies (DPES)	1971	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)
New Zealand Election Study (NZES)	1990	New Zealand Election Study (NZES)
Norwegian National Election Studies (NNES)	1957	Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD)
Polish National Election Study (PGSW)	1997	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
Portuguese Election Study (CEP)	2002	Production and Archive of Social Science Data (PASSDA)
Spanish Election Studies (CIS)	1977	Centro de Investigacion Sociológica (CIS)
Swedish National Election Studies (SNES)	1960	Swedish National Data Archive (SND)
Swiss Election Study (Selects)	1971	FORS
American National Election Study (ANES)	1948	American National Election Study (ANES)

Study Program	Since	Data Provider
Comparative Study of Electoral Systems	1996	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
The European Voter / TEV	1956-1998	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
European Election Study (EES)	1979	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
Making Electoral Democracy Work (MEDW)	2010-2015	Harvard Dataverse
European Social Survey (ESS)	2002	European Social Survey (ESS)
International Social Survey Program (ISSP)	1985	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften

4. Concluding remarks

User community involvement is seen as essential for the successful development of a Knowledge Graph in electoral studies. This report specified ways in which the relevant user community can be identified and approached and summarised tasks in which user community involvement can be concretised.

In view of the Covid-19 crisis original plans for user involvement had to be cancelled, and equivalent forms are being developed in which members of the user community of electoral studies can be involved in the development of the pilot-Knowledge Graph in online ways.

At the moment of writing it cannot be predicted yet how successful these online forms will be, in terms of mobilisation of members of the user community and in terms of the effectiveness of their involvement. It can therefore also not yet be foreseen whether this –and other– fallout from the pandemic may result in a need for adaptation of the time planning of the development and production of the pilot-Knowledge Graph.¹³

5. References

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¹³ This time planning is detailed in the report of Deliverable 9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*).